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SOME LATE ROMAN INSCRIPTIONS FROM SIDE

Abstract: This article presents five late antique inscriptions found in Side in the last few years. The first inscription concerns the construction of the Arcadian Forum consecrated by a governor. The second and third inscriptions refer to construction work in the main street, mentioning the name of a *pater civitatis*, Georgius. The fourth one was set up in honour of Helena, mother of Constantine the Great. The last one records donations by Conon and Modestus, two lectors of a church.

Among the new epigraphic material found during excavation work in the two colonnaded streets and during the restoration of the theatre there are several inscriptions from the late Roman period. They can be categorized into three groups: building inscriptions (no. 1–4), one honorific inscription (no. 5) and a donation. Only one inscription commemorating donations by Conon and Modestus, two lectors of a church, comes from outside the city. It was brought to the Side Museum from the ruins of Karaevli Mahallesi near the village Taşağıl. These ruins lie only some 10 km to the east of Aspendos, which suggests that the small settlement belonged not to Side but to her rival on the Eurymedon.¹

1. Arcadian Forum

A profiled basis found near the Nymphaion during clearing work at the city gate. The inscription cannot be reconstructed completely, as the right half of the stone is missing.

H: 1.65 m; L: 0.53 m; D: 0.5 m; LH: 0.06–7 m.

- τὸν φόρο[ν τοῦτον?]
 2 Ἄρκαδι[ακὸν τὸν ἐ]-
 πώνυ[μον τοῦ δεσ]-
 4 πότου [τῆς οἰκουμέ]-
 νης Ἄρ[καδίου, . . .]
 6 Οὐίκρ[ιος ? -ca.7-]
 ὁ λάμ. [ἀνθ. -ca.7-]
 8 τη αὐ[-----ca. 10----]
 καθειέ[ρωσεν].

[...] *Vicerius, the glorious [governor], dedicated the Arcadian Forum named after the emperor of the inhabited (world) Arcadius, to his [fatherland?].*

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The letters are typical of the 5th century: lunar sigma and epsilon; the omega is written in minuscule; phi, rho and epsilon were carved taller than other letters.

L. 1: Here the Greek word φόρος is used for the Latin “*forum*” The restoration τὸν φόρο[ν τοῦτον] fills the 7–8 letter gap quite satisfactorily.

L. 6: Dated to the mid 2nd century AD by Clemens Bosch, an inscription from Ancyra mentions a certain Flavius *Vicerius* Aphrodisius who offered his vows to Isis.² In our inscription “Vicerius” may be the name of the governor who consecrated the forum. Perhaps the previous line contained an abbreviated nomen gentilicium (e.g. Flavius).³

L. 7: ὁ λάμ(πρότατος) [ἀνθ(ύπατος)] / ὁ λάμ(πρότατος) [ἀνθύπατος] | τῇ αὐ[τοῦ πατρίδι]?. An abbreviation mark for λάμ(πρότατος) is engraved over the “M”.

The forum was consecrated by a governor who was probably of consular rank (λαμπρότατος). As for the governor’s title, ἀνθύπατος seems most convenient, as its number of letters exactly fits gap, while the other candidates (κόμης or ἡγέμων) are too short. This restoration is also suitable for the status of the province, which seems to have kept its consular status at least until the reign of Justinian.⁴

A similar inscription from the same city area in Side reads: τὸν φόρον τὸν Ἀρκα|διακὸν τὸν ἐπών|μον τοῦ δεσπότη| τῆς οἰκου(μένης). However, the inscription was presented by Bosch as unfinished.⁵ Johannes Nollé, referring to the construction of the Arcadian Forum in Constantinople after the suppression of the Gainas uprising in 400/402, suggested that this unfin-

² E. Bosch, *Quellen zur Geschichte der Stadt Ankara im Altertum* (Ankara 1967), p. 250, no. 186: κυρία Ἰσιδι | Φλ(άουιος) Οὐίκριος | Ἀφροδείσιος | εὐχῆς χάριν | ἀνέστησα.

³ For Vicrius (Vicerius, Vicirius) s. W. Schulze, *Zur Geschichte lateinischer Eigennamen* (Berlin 1904), 102.

⁴ In *Notitia*, which belongs to 5th century, Pamphylia was listed as a consular province under the diocese of Asiana (*Notitia Dignitatum*, Or. I); Hierocles 679,1. However, in the meantime, Leo I established several new military command posts under a *comes* (Cod. Iust. 12.59.10), amongst which were Pisidia, Pamphylia, Lycaonia and Isauria, possibly established against the wide-ranging Isaurian banditry that threatened the security of the Taurus regions, see: A. H. M. Jones, *The Later Roman Empire 284–602. A Social, Economic and Administrative Survey* (Oxford 1964), p. 224; H. Brandt, *Gesellschaft und Wirtschaft Pamphyliens und Pisidiens im Altertum* (Bonn 1992), pp. 197–198.

⁵ A. M. Mansel – E. Bosch – J. İnan, 1947 *Senesi Side Kazılarında Dair Öneriler* (Ankara 1951), pp. 46–80 no. 32; J. and L. Robert, *Bull. Epigr.* 1951, no. 219a; J. Nollé, *Side im Altertum. Geschichte und Zeugnisse II* (Bonn 2001), no. 166.

ished inscription might have been erected between 402 and 408.⁶ The present inscription too belongs to the reign of the eastern emperor Arcadius (AD 383–408). It was set up after 395 when he assumed sole rule of the eastern empire. Perhaps we can date the inscription even more precisely. In 404 AD Roman forces under the command of Arbazicus beat the Isaurians. Zosimus⁷ reports that thanks to the Roman victory the Pamphylians were rescued from the Isaurians, who used to plunder the Pamphylian Plain from their hiding places in the Taurus mountain range. Perhaps the forum was built when after the Roman victory the situation in the area had calmed down.

Both forum inscriptions were discovered in front of the *nymphaion* near the city gate, which supports Arif Müfid Mansel's view that the Arcadian Forum may have been built in the paved area between the city gate and the *nymphaion*.⁸ Consequently, Clive Foss seems to have been mistaken in his opinion that the unfinished inscription was moved there from some other place, e.g. the Roman agora near the theatre where he believes the Arcadian Forum was.⁹

2. Georgius, a pater civitatis

Profiled white marble column-base erected in front of a Byzantine workshop on the south side of the main street, some 75 m west of the Grand Gate, now in the garden of the Side Museum.

Inv: C-4.

H.: 0.33 m; Br.: 0.40 m; T.: 0.37 m; Bh.: 0.04 m.

† ἐπὶ Γεωρ-
2 γίου τοῦ λογ(ισιότατ)ου
σχο(λαστικοῦ) κ(αί) πατρός
4 ἰνδ(ικτιόνι) ζ' †

Under Georgius, the most eloquent scholasticus and father (of the city). 6th year of the current) indiction.

L.2 λογισιότατου = λογιωτάτου; A above T, O above X indicate the abbreviated words.

⁶ Nollé, *ibid.* p. 487.

⁷ Zosimus, *Historia Nova* 5.25.2.4–6: τούτων ἀπαγγελθέντων Ἀρβαζάκιος ἐκπέμπεται στρατηγός ὡς δὴ τοῖς ἐν Παμφυλίᾳ πράγμασι πονοῦσιν ἐπὶ κουρήσων; for more about Isaurian raids of 404 see Johannes Chrysostomus, *Epistulae* 14.4; cf. D. Woods, Arbazacius, Fravitta, and the Government of Isauria CA A. D. 396–404, *Phoenix* 52 (1998), pp. 109–119.

⁸ A. M. Mansel, *Side. 1947–1966 Yılları Kazıları ve Araştırmalarının Sonuçları* (Ankara 1978), p. 16.

⁹ C. Foss, Attius Philippus and the Walls of Side, *ZPE* 26 (1977), 179 fn. 25 (= Foss, *History and Archaeology of Byzantine Asia Minor* [Aldershot 1990], VIII).

L. 3: πατρός for πατήρ τῆς πόλεως or Lat. *pater civitatis*.¹⁰

In Side, there are two more inscriptions from the fifth to sixth centuries AD, attesting two different πατέρες, Theodorus and Fronto.¹¹ The official position of πατήρ τῆς πόλεως is known from the mid 5th AD century onwards¹². The “fathers” of a city mostly dealt with the construction work, though they were also concerned with erecting statues or even setting up game boards.¹³ So, this inscription (together with no. 3) indicates to some construction or conversion work in the main street. In order to be a *scholasticus*, a title which appears in texts from the 4th century onwards, Georgius must have received thorough legal training¹⁴. His title of λογιώτατος, which is a very rare,¹⁵ is identical with the widespread epithet ἐλλογιμώτατος (*eloquentissimus*)¹⁶ customarily attached to *scholastici* and *patres*. Charlotte Roueché, emphasizing that this is a professional qualification rather than an official honour, considers this title to be more or less equivalent to today's “Dr.” or “M.A.”¹⁷ She therefore believes that the cities *patres* enjoyed a remarkable degree of independence and must have been prosperous.¹⁸

On the basis of the shape of the letters and of the title πατήρ τῆς πόλεως, the inscription can be dated to the mid 5th century or early 6th century.¹⁹

The inscription is quite similar to the inscription corrected below (no.3), and presumably this Georgius is identical with Georgius in no. 3.

3. Nollé, I. v. Side 164a revised

A column-base of white marble, found in the main street near no. 2. Now in the garden of the museum.

Inv: C-1.

H.: 1.23 m; L.: 0.84 m; D.: 0.75 m; Lh.: 0.06–0.08 m (stigma: 0.12 m).

¹⁰ For detailed information on πατήρ τῆς πόλεως see: Ch. Roueché, A New Inscription from Aphrodisias and the Title πατήρ τῆς πόλεως, *GRBS* 20 (1979), 173–185; Ch. Roueché, Aphrodisias in Late Antiquity (London 1989), 76–80.

¹¹ For Theodorus: A. M. Mansel – G. E. Bean – J. İnan, Side agorası ve civarındaki binalar. 1948 Yılı kazılarında dair rapor (Ankara 1956), p. 90, no. 70; L. Robert, *RevPhil* 32 (1958), 47 ff.; Nollé, I. v. Side no. 164. For Fronto: G. E. Bean, Inscriptions of Side (Ankara 1965), no.87 and *Bull. Epigr.* 1965, 419; Nollé, I. v. Side, no. 149.

¹² Roueché 1979, p. 182 and 1989, p. 77.

¹³ For instance, in Aphrodisias their responsibilities can be better understood through inscriptions. For building work in Aphrodisias see Roueché 1989, nos. 38, 42, 43, 44, 61, 85, 86, 87 and for statutes no.62, even for game boards nos. 68–69. And for other inscriptions and legislative texts in various places see: Roueché 1979, pp. 176–182.

¹⁴ Lampe (Patristic Lexicon) defines σχολαστικός as *one who has passed through the σχολή τῶν γραμματῶν, one with a general education or advocate, lawyer*, cf. Roueché 1989, p. 76.

¹⁵ An instance from Ephesos: D. Knibbe – B. İplikçioğlu, *JÖAI* 53 (1981–1982), 125 no. 124 (= *SEG* 33, 961): ... τῶν λογιωτάτων σχολαστικῶν καὶ πατέρων.

¹⁶ O. Hornickel, Ehren- und Rangprädikate in den Papyrusurkunden. Ein Beitrag zum römischen und byzantinischen Titelwesen (Gießen 1930), pp. 7–8 (ἐλλογιμώτατος), pp. 27–8 (λογιώτατος).

¹⁷ Roueché 1989, 77.

¹⁸ Roueché 1979, 184.

¹⁹ Considering the *indictio* given as 6, we might have the possible options of years 453, 468, 483, 498, 513, 528 and 543.

Ed.: Nollé, *Side im Altertum. Geschichte und Zeugnisse II* (Bonn 2001 [IK 43–44]), no.164a.

Nollé's reading:

[ἀνενεώ-]
 [θη ή στοά ?]
 ἐπί . [. . .]-
 2 γίου τοῦ λ[ο]-
 γιστά. σχο. καὶ
 4 πατρός
 ἰνδ. ζ'

According to Nollé the inscription had two more lines at the beginning. He suggested Pelagius for the name of πατήρ and filled the gap before the ending ...γιου in second line with Πελα.

In the light of the new inscription I don't see a necessity for the additional first two lines. It is perfectly possible to read the letter after ἐπί as Γ. For this reason, I suggest:

ἐπί Γ[εωρ]-
 2 γίου τοῦ λ[ο]-
 γιστά(του) σχο(λαστικοῦ) καὶ
 4 πατρός
 ἰνδ(ικτιόνι) ζ'

*Under Georgius, most eloquent scholastic and father (of the city).
 6th year of the current) indiction.*

L.2–3 λογιστάτου = λογιωτάτου; Alpha over Tau ($\overset{\wedge}{\tau}$) and omikron over chi ($\overset{\circ}{\chi}$) indicate the abbreviated words λ[ο]γιστά(του) σχο(λαστικοῦ) of line 3.

L. 4: πατρός means πατήρ τῆς πόλεως or Lat. *pater civitatis*.

For the commentary see the previous inscription.

The fact that both inscriptions were found in the colonnaded street and Georgius renovated at least some of the columns suggests that this street underwent some modification by the time of his ministry.

4. An honorific inscription for Helena, mother of Constantine the Great

White marble statue-base found in the scene area of the theatre, now in the agora in front of the theatre.

A profile on the left-hand side. The reverse was left rough. The inscribed face was cut vertically, possibly for a different purpose. It shows features of a late antique inscription (letter style, such as cornered sigma; bêta is carved narrowly).

The inscription consists of four lines.

Inv.: P2. 215.

H: 1.65 m; L: 0.85 m; D: 0.95 m; Lh: 0.06 (3rd line)–0.09 m (1st line).

[ή λαμπρα]

- 2 Σιδ[ητῶν μητρόπολις]
 Ἐλέ[νην αὐγυσταν, τήν]
 μητέρα Αὐγύστου, τήν]
 4 βασ[ίλισσαν.....]

The glorious metropolis of Sidetans (honoured) Helena Augusta, mother of the Augustus, the empress ...

This is the third honorific inscription in Side for Helena, mother of Constantine the Great.²⁰ Like the two other inscriptions, this inscription had not been erected before 18th September 324 when the Battle of Chrysopolis in which Licinius was defeated was fought (at that time Side was under the control of Licinius). The inscription was probably set up between 324 and 328/329 AD. During this period Helena went on a pilgrimage to the Holy Land in 326/327 before she died in 328/329 AD. On her journey Helena is said to have visited Side.²¹

5. Donations of Conon and Modestus

White marble block, now in the garden of Side Museum. Its reverse shows ornamented palm branches. The stone was probably a parapet slab in previous usage.

Finding spot: Karaevli Örenyeri near the village Taşağıl, some 10 km east of Aspendos.

H: 38 cm; L: 107 cm; D: 10.5 cm; Lh: 2.3–2.6 cm.

- | | | | |
|---|--------------------|-------|--------------------------|
| | εὐχή Κων- | | εὐχή Μοδέστου |
| 2 | νος ἀναγνώ- | Cross | ἀναγνώστου, νό(μισμα) α' |
| | στου, νό(μισμα) α' | | |

²⁰ J. Nollé, *Side im Altertum. Geschichte und Zeugnisse. Band I–II* [IK 43–44] (Bonn I :1993, II:2001), nos. 47 (Ἐλένην τήν βασιλισσαν, τήν μητέρα τοῦ Αὐγούστου, ἡ λαμπρά Σιδητῶν μητρόπολις) and 48 (Ἐλένην μητέρα Αὐγούστου).

²¹ *ibid.* 322 pp.

Vow of lector Conon, 1 solidus – Vow of lector Modestus, 1 solidus.

L.3 νόμισμα was abbreviated as Ν, examples of this abbreviation can be found in Side and elsewhere.²²

An inscription from Klazomenai provides an example of similar use of εὐχή is in the same context (ὕπερ εὐχῆς Πατρ[- καὶ] Ἡσυχίας συμ[βίου] νομίσματα δ[ύο]).²³

The position of ἀναγνώστης is the initial post towards becoming deacon, priest or bishop. It is the first step in the clerical *cursus honorum*.²⁴ Their primary duty is all about reading liturgical lections, Scriptures etc. Their chief was called πρωταναγνώστης. These clerical officials were known from various inscriptions.²⁵ These two lectors, Conon and Modestus, each donated one solidus to a church, to which this stone probably belonged and where it was probably exhibited.

²² Side: Nollé, I. v. Side, nos. 236–237; Olbia (Kemer): S. Şahin, Olbia und einige andere Küstenorte bei Kemer in Westpamphylien, *EA* 33 (2001), p. 151. This inscription was revised by A. Łajtar, Zu einer christlichen Mosaikinschrift aus Ostlykien, *EA* 35 (2003), p. 123–4 = *SEG* 51, 1820.

²³ H. Grégoire, Recueil des inscriptions grecques chrétiennes d'Asie Mineure (Paris 1922), no. 91; H. Engelmann – R. Merkelbach, Die Inschriften von Erythrai und Klazomenai I–II (Bonn 1972–1973), no. 532.

²⁴ Lampe, Patristic Lexicon, pp. 99–100, s.v. ἀναγνώστης.

²⁵ For ἀναγνώστης: Grégoire no. 148 (Samos); 226 (= I. v. Didyma 612); I. v. Ephesos 1285.18; TAM 4.1 374 (Nicomedia); C. Haspels, The Highlands of Phrygia (New Jersey 1971), p. 318, no. 50; p. 320, no. 54 and p. 339f. no. 108; Roueché 1989, no. 91 (Aphrodisias); Şahin 2001, p. 151 (Pamphylia) and Łajtar 2003, p. 123–4 (= *SEG* 51 1820). For πρωταναγνώστης: Roueché 1989, 115 (Aphrodisias); W. H. Buckler – D. M. Robinson, Sardis VII. Greek and Latin Inscriptions (Leyden 1932), p. 147f. no. 188.